

27.04.2024

RESEARCHER MENTAL HEALTH

OVERVIEW IN MONTENEGRO

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COST ACTION CA19117 - Researcher Mental Health (ReMO)

Cite This Document: Osmanovic, S., (2024). *Researcher Mental Health Overview in Montenegro*. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11082629>

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Country profile

Capital: Podgorica
Language: Montenegrin
Currency: Euro

Total area of the country 13 812 km² [1]

Total population 633 158 [2]

17.91% - under 14 years old

66.18% - between 15 and 64 years old

15.91% - 65 years and older [3]

48,4% males and 50,6% females

Women in the labour force - 44%
compared to men (2020)

Women researchers - 50%
compared to men researchers (2018) [4]

GDP per capita: 9 252 [5]

Income Group (World Bank) Upper-middle
Montenegro ranks 75th among the 132 economies
featured in the GII 2023 [6]

Average monthly salary:

February 2024: average earnings (gross) 1 026 euro, average (net) earnings (without taxes and contributions) 821 euro [7]

Average monthly salaries for university teachers: gross salary (including taxes and contributions) 3,711 EUR (range 1,751 EUR - 5,810 EUR), (varying by the education level, academic title, experience, administrative engagement, and bonuses) [8]

Unemployment rate: Long-term unemployed (12 months or more) as % of the total active population 2022 is 10,2 [9]

UN World Happiness Index [10]

2023: Montenegro ranks 67 among 156 countries (calculated based on "GDP, life expectancy, generosity, social support, freedom, and corruption, compared to the imaginary country Dystopia")

2012 - Start of accession negotiations with the European Union (EU) [11]

[1] [2] MONSTAT (2020). Crna Gora u brojkama 2020 <https://monstat.org/uploads/files/publikacije/CG%20u%20brojkama%202020%20MNE.pdf>

[3] Montenegro Population (2024) <https://countrymeters.info/en/Montenegro>

[4] <https://w3.unece.org/CountriesInFigures/en/Home/Index?countryCode=499>

[5] MONSTAT, Statistical Yearbook (2023) <https://www.monstat.org/uploads/files/publikacije/godisnjak%202023/31.pdf>

[6] Montenegro ranking in the Global Innovation Index 2023 <https://www.wipo.int/edocs/pubdocs/en/wipo-pub-2000-2023/me.pdf>

[7] MONSTAT 2024, Average earnings (wages) February 2024 https://www.monstat.org/uploads/files/zarade/2024/2/RAD_EN_Februar_2024.pdf

[8] Average University Teacher Salary in Montenegro for 2024. World Salaries. Retrieved from <https://worldsalaries.com/average-university-teacher-salary-in-montenegro/>.

[9] MONSTAT, Statistical Yearbook (2023) <https://www.monstat.org/uploads/files/publikacije/godisnjak%202023/31.pdf>

[10] <https://countryeconomy.com/demography/world-happiness-index>

[11] <https://www.skupstina.me/en/eu-accession/montenegro-and-the-european-union>

Mental health support and service system in Montenegro

Based on the Constitution, Montenegro is a state of social justice in which everyone has the right to health care [12]. MH protection is embedded in the Constitution, Law on Health Care [13] and the Law on the Protection and the Exercise of the Rights of Mentally Disabled Persons [14]. The Montenegrin Law on Safety and Health at Work [15] is focused on “providing working conditions that do not lead to injuries at work, occupational and work-related diseases while also creating conditions for full physical and psychological safety of employees”. It does not specifically address mental health at work as such, nor its protection.

The Montenegrin system of implementing mental health care and psychosocial support services is organised on three levels: primary, secondary, and tertiary. The public health care services are free for citizens, but the waiting lists are long at all three levels due to insufficient staff, the increased numbers of patients [16], and in some cases, the inability to treat certain categories of residents (social patients) [17]. Besides being supported through the mental health centres that are part of the public health system, citizens can also seek private professional support, which they have to pay for. On the primary level, in cooperation with schools and the NGO sector, there are counselling centres for young people. They provide individual, voluntary, and confidential counselling and group preventive workshops.

In 2019, the Government of Montenegro adopted a Strategy for the Protection and Improvement of Mental Health in Montenegro for 2019–2023 [18]. There are four priority areas covered by the strategy:

- promotion of mental health and prevention of mental disorders;
- improving capacities for early diagnosing, treatment, and rehabilitation of persons with mental health disorders;
- respecting and protecting the human rights of persons with mental health disorders, and
- mental health information systems and research studies in this area.

[12] Constitution of Montenegro. Official Gazette of Montenegro, nos. 1/2007 and 38/2013

[13] The Law on Health Care (2020). Official Gazette of Montenegro, nos. 3/2016, 39/2016, 2/2017, 44/2018, 24/2019 and 82/2020.

[14] Zakon o zaštiti i ostvarivanju prava mentalno obojelijih lica [Law on the Protection and the Exercise of the Rights of Mentally Disabled Persons]. Official Gazette of the Republic of Montenegro, nos. 32/2005 and 27/2013. <https://www.gov.me/dokumenta/7bf86572-bc2d-45ff-a342-7a9195a53303>

[15] Zakon o zaštiti i zdravlju na radu

Official Gazette of Montenegro, no. 34/14, 044/18 <https://www.gov.me/dokumenta/a6a538b0-4884-45fc-8ab8-2240af84c805>

[16] <https://www.cin-cg.me/crna-gora-nema-funkcionalne-centre-za-mentalno-zdravlje-broj-pacijenata-raste-a-ljekara-nema-dovoljno/>

[17] ombudsman.co.me/zastitaiprevencija/59.news_report.html

[18] Strategija zaštite i unapređenja mentalnog zdravlja u Crnoj Gori 2019–2023

<https://www.gov.me/dokumenta/60af25aa-a65e-4957-84d8-e77a3182ab9b>

Mental health support and service system in Montenegro

In reporting on the realisation of the Action plans for the implementation of the Strategy, it is stated that the majority of the activities could not have been carried out due to the COVID-19 pandemic and limited financial resources [19]. Media promotion of mental health was the focal area that was well implemented. Journalists engaged in research journalism were educated in exploring and writing about mental health issues. In addition, scoping through the media, journals and social networks, it could be noted that Mental Health Day was organised and used as an opportunity to talk in public about mental health issues and needs in this field.

During the Covid-19 pandemic, in November 2021, almost a third of people in Montenegro (30%), age 18 and older reported having an impression that their psychological health has deteriorated [20]. Majority reported feeling optimistic (58%) and happy (57%), but 44% also reported feeling worried. As stressed in the public poll carried out by IPSOS, UNICEF Montenegro and Association of Psychologists of Montenegro, three out of five citizens (60%) said they were ready to ask for mental health professional support.

In 2021, in an effort to make mental health support more accessible to children and adolescents, the Ministry of Finance and Social Affairs launched the national campaign Call When You Are in Trouble. The National SOS phone service offers anonymous conversations with trained professionals and advice to young people, 0-24. Also in 2021, in the capital of Montenegro, Podgorica, a House of Health was initiated as the free service for citizens needing psychosocial support. Psychologists, social workers and physicians from public institutions with the support from the Association of Psychologists of Montenegro and prominent NGOs carry out various preventive activities, including educating on mental health issues [21].

[19] Godišnji izvještaj o realizaciji Akcionog plana 2021-2023 za sprovođenje Strategije zaštite i unapređenja mentalnog zdravlja u Crnoj Gori 2019-2023, u 2022. godini. <https://www.gov.me/clanak/godisnji-izvjestaj-o-realizaciji-akcionog-plana-2021-2023-za-sprovođenje-strategije-zastite-i-unapređenja-mentalnog-zdravlja-u-crnoj-gori-2019-2023-u-2022-godini>

[20] <https://www.unicef.org/montenegro/sites/unicef.org.montenegro/files/2021-12/Nacionalno%20reprezentativno%20istra%C5%BEivanje%20-%20mentalno%20zdravlje%20.pdf>

[21] <https://starisajt.podgorica.me/vijesti/3386>

Mental health support and service system in Montenegro

In order to raise the awareness of mental health issues and promote mental health initiatives across the country, in 2023 the Institute for Public Health and Clinical Centre of Montenegro [22] organised the first Mental Health Festival in Montenegro with “empathy” as a main theme. The festival lasted for 10 days. It was organised in partnership with numerous institutions, organisations, and experts, altogether 24 stakeholders. It was stressed that mental health should be perceived in the context of all other areas of life.

Limited engagement in mental health awareness initiatives can be attributed to several factors [23]. Firstly, the enduring stigma surrounding mental health often deters individuals from seeking support or openly discussing their struggles. Secondly, inadequate funding and resources allocated to mental health programs hinder active participation by organisations and institutions. Additionally, some entities may lack awareness of the importance of mental health initiatives or prioritise other issues. Lastly, difficulties in accessing information about mental health awareness initiatives and resources further impede effective engagement.

Mental health care billboard Podgorica
March 2024 Photo: I. B. Petrovic

[22] Clinical Centre of Montenegro and The Institute of Public Health (2023). Svjetski dan mentalnog zdravlja "Naše glave, naša prava", <https://kccg.me/vijesti/svjetski-dan-mentalnog-zdravlja-nase-glave-nasa-prava>

[23] <https://kccg.me/vijesti/mentalno-zdravlje-i-blagostanje-globalni-prioriteti/>

What is in the news?

Glance to the general media and scientific papers

News

Mental health is somewhat discussed in the Montenegrin media. Some of the striking headlines during the 2023 were:

- 📰 How much does mental health cost? [24]
- 📰 Until December 1st, 107 Montenegrin citizens committed suicide [25]
- 📰 Suicide every third day: In seven years, 784 people took their own lives [26]
- 📰 Raise awareness of the importance of mental health [27]
- 📰 The mental health clinic is to be completed by the end of January [28]
- 📰 Employees and mental health: Young and worn out [29]
- 📰 The first free appointment with a psychiatrist in KCCG at the beginning of July: How much does mental health cost [30]
- 📰 Working together to create an environment where mental health is valued, protected and promoted [31]
- 📰 Montenegro without a department of psychiatry for children [32]
- 📰 HRA (Human Rights Action): In Montenegro, there are no adequate conditions for the treatment of persons with mental illnesses [33]

On the other hand, some of the titles of papers dealing with mental health issues in Montenegro that were published in international scientific journals add to this picture:

- (2023) Mental-Health-Related Stigma in a Conservative and Patriarchal Community [34]
- (2021) Trends in suicide mortality in Montenegro from 2000 to 2018 [35]
- (2020) No research for the decisionally-impaired mentally ill: a view from Montenegro [36]

In Montenegro, political news and affairs dominate the daily news. However, a close exploration of political statements and programs reveals a striking absence of mental health as an issue. Analyses of political agendas and parliamentary discussions indicate a conspicuous lack of emphasis on mental health. Politicians seldomly address mental health directly, with the term "mental health" rarely featuring in their rhetoric. References to mental health are often relegated to colloquial expressions or dismissive remarks, such as questioning one's sanity. Mental health is conspicuously absent as a priority on the agendas of major political parties in Montenegro.

This lack of attention to mental health within political discourse raises concerns about the prioritisation of mental health initiatives and the overall support for mental health services and awareness campaigns within Montenegro. As mental health continues to be a pressing global concern, it is high time for political leaders and policymakers to acknowledge its importance and take proactive steps towards promoting mental well-being within Montenegrin society.

[24] <https://rtcg.me/vijesti/drustvo/425462/koliko-kosta-mentalno-zdravlje.html>

[25] <https://rtcg.me/hronika/497451/do-1-decembra-samoubistvo-izvrsilo-107-crnogorskih-gradjana.html>

[26] <https://en.vijesti.me/news/black-chronicle/650669/suicide-every-third-day-for-seven-years-784-people-took-their-own-livesana.html>

[27] <https://www.aktuelno.me/crna-gora/podici-svijest-o-vaznosti-mentalnog-zdravlja/>

[28] <https://mina.news/vijesti-iz-crne-gore/klinika-za-mentalno-zdravlje-bice-završena-krajem-januara/>

[29] <https://www.rtvbudva.me/vijesti/zaposleni-i-mentalno-zdravlje-mladi-i-potroseni/70213>

[30] <https://standard.co.me/drustvo/prvi-slobodan-termin-kod-psihijatra-u-kccg-u-pocetkom-jula-koliko-kosta-mentalno-zdravlje>

[31] <https://www.portalanalitika.me/clanak/zajednicki-raditi-na-stvaranju-okruzenja-u-kojem-se-mentalno-zdravlje-cijeni-stiti-i-promovise>

[32] <https://www.portalanalitika.me/clanak/crna-gora-bez-odjeljenja-psihijatrije-za-djecu>

[33] <https://www.vijesti.me/vijesti/drustvo/677158/hra-u-crnoj-gori-ne-postoje-adekvatni-uslovi-za-lijecenje-osoba-sa-mentalnim-obiljenjima>

[34] Popović, A., & Marić, N. (2023). Mental-health-related stigma in a conservative and patriarchal community. *Social Sciences*, 12(5), 262.

<https://www.mdpi.com/2076-0760/12/5/262>

[35] Injac Stevović, L., Repišti, S., Radojičić, T., & Injac, O. (2021). Trends in suicide mortality in Montenegro from 2000 to 2018. *Annals of General Psychiatry*, 20, 1-6. <https://annals-general-psychiatry.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12991-021-00337-3>

[36] Dakić, T. (2020). No research for the decisionally-impaired mentally ill: a view from Montenegro. *BMC Medical Ethics*, 21(1), 1-9.

<https://bmcomedethics.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12910-020-00489-z>

Academia and academic research in Montenegro

Higher education

As an activity of public interest, higher education (HE) in Montenegro is regulated by the Law on Higher Education [37]. HE institutions are autonomous in their work (in the field of teaching, research, and artistic work). Education is accessible to everyone, without any restrictions. Improving, developing, and securing the quality of HE are the responsibilities of the Council for Higher Education and the Agency for Control and Quality Assurance of Higher Education (ACAQHE). As Montenegro is a part of the European Higher Education Area (EHEA), ACAQHE works in line with European standards and guidelines. Institutions of higher education are either public or private - universities, faculties, and colleges. Institutions must be accredited and then reaccredited every five years, and that is one of the conditions for licensing by the Ministry of Education.

There are seven licensed institutions of higher education - four universities and three independent faculties [38]. In accordance with the Higher Education Law [39], higher education is structured into three tiers: undergraduate studies (3 years bachelor level, 180 ECTS), postgraduate studies (specialist degree and master level - 120 ECTS), and doctoral studies 3 years, 180 ECTS). As licensed by the Ministry of Education and accredited by the ACAQE, in Montenegro, there are 278 study programs. At the public university - University of Montenegro, bachelor and master studies are free of charge. In the past ten years, on the average, the total number of enrolled students was 24,500, and the number of graduates was 4,800. Of that number, 70% were enrolled and graduated at the only public university, University of Montenegro [40].

[37] [39] Law on Higher Education (2023). Official Gazette of Montenegro, nos. 044/2014; 052/2014; 047/2015; 040/2016; 042/2017; 071/2017; 055/2018; 003/2019; 017/2019; 047/2019; 072/2019; 074/2020; 104/2021; 086/2022; 125/2023.

https://www.ucg.ac.me/skladiste/blog_6/objava_159199/fajlovi/00-0102%20Law%20on%20Higher%20Education.pdf

[38] [40] <https://akokvo.me/ustanove-visokog-obrazovanja/>

Academia and academic research in Montenegro

Table: Number of enrolled and graduated students in Montenegro in 2022/2023

	Enrolled in 2022/2023			Graduated in 2022		
	Total	Women	Men	Total	Women	Men
Undergraduate studies	16883	9764	7119	2430	1475	955
Specialist	1158	597	561	838	503	335
Master	3008	1953	1055	429	304	125
Doctoral studies	128	67	61	27	17	10

Source: Monstat, Department for education, culture and justice
<https://www.monstat.org/eng/page.php?id=339&pageid=74>

Based on the latest available data on enrollment in postgraduate and doctoral studies, in the academic year 2023/2024, there are 3920 students enrolled in postgraduate and doctoral studies at institutions of higher education in Montenegro [41]. There are 3256 students enrolled at master studies. Compared to the number of students enrolled in specialist studies in the previous academic year, the number of students (432) decreased by 62.7%.

There are 232 students enrolled in PhD programs. As they have the strongest research potential, it is interesting to note the gender breakdown: there are 55% women and 45% men.

[41] <https://www.monstat.org/uploads/files/obrazovanje/visoko/upisani2024/Upis%20na%20postdiplomske%20i%20doktorske%20studije.pdf>

Academia and academic research in Montenegro

There are four universities in Montenegro [42]

University of Montenegro UCG
University of Donja Gorica UDG
Mediterranean University
Adriatic University

University of Montenegro (UCG)

Public university, founded in 1974.

Seat of the University is the capital city, Podgorica, which is also home to the largest number of faculties. Other faculties are spread in three Montenegrin regions: central, northern, and southern, in Nikšić, Cetinje, Kotor, Bar, Igalo, Berane and Bijelo Polje.

There are:

- 19 faculties and 3 research institutes
- 168 study programs
- about 17,000 active students
- more than 1,000 academic, professional, and other staff

The University of Montenegro is a member of prestigious international organisations such as: EUA (The European University Association), Magna Charta Universitatum, AUF (The Francophone University Association), Uniadrion (The University Network of the Adriatic Ionian Initiative), NUSCT (Network of Universities of Small Countries and Territories), and BUA (The Balkan University Association).

<https://www.ucg.ac.me>

University of Donja Gorica (UDG)

Private university, founded in 2007.

Seat of the UDG and all the faculties is within one building in Podgorica municipality, Donja Gorica.

There are:

- 12 faculties
- 18 study programs
- 3000 students
- over 300 professors, associates, and researchers from various fields

<https://www.udg.edu.me/>

Academia and academic research in Montenegro

Mediterranean University

Private university, founded 2006.

There are:

- 6 faculties
- 9 study programs

<https://unimediterran.net/>

Adriatic University

Private university established in 2017.
Located in Bar.

There are:

- 7 faculties situated along the Montenegrin coast

<https://www.univerzitetadriatik.com/>

Academia and academic research in Montenegro

Research system

Based on the objectives of higher education, it is clear that higher education is closely intertwined with research activities.

The research system of Montenegro is under the Ministry of Science and Technological Development, MSTD [43]. The Law on Scientific Research Activity regulates the organisation, conditions, and financing of scientific research activities. Scientific research is defined as an activity of public interest.

Scientific research entails basic (fundamental), applied, and developmental research organised in six fields: natural-mathematical, technical-technological, medical, agricultural, social, and humanities, as well as interdisciplinary research.

Research is primarily carried out by the Montenegrin Academy of Sciences and Arts, scientific research institutions, and institutions of higher education, including public and private universities.

In particular, the strategy of scientific research establishes scientific research priorities, plans for supporting young researchers in priority research areas, research funds for financing programs of general interest, and deals with scientific research infrastructure and scientific information systems. It is proposed by the Scientific Research Council and adopted by the Government of Montenegro on a five year cycle.

Scientific research work is carried out through scientific research programs and projects. The Ministry allocates the amount of funding available for scientific research. Funding of the programs of public interest is determined based on the competition. The MSTD issues the conditions that must be met by the researchers and heads of the scientific research programs and projects.

The scientific research activity is carried out by the scientific research institutions and their work is regulated by the Law on Scientific Research Activity. There are public and private research organisations. Scientific research is carried out by persons with a research title and persons with a scientific title engaged in research organisations, as well as persons elected to academic and associate positions at institutions of higher education. All research institutions must be licensed by the MSTD. Licensing is on five-year terms.

The European Commission 2023 Report for Montenegro, favourably assessed development in the field of science and research. [44] It is noted that the new Law on higher education and the Strategy on higher education for 2023-2027 are underway. The country benefits from more intensive international cooperation (outgoing and incoming mobilities) as part of the Erasmus+ programme. As a participant in strengthening the European research area, the University of Montenegro was awarded EUAXESS HR Excellence in Research recognition in 2020. [45]

[43] Law on Scientific Research Activity. (2020). Official Gazette of Montenegro, nos. 80/2010, 40/2011, 57/2014, 082/2020. <https://akokvo.me/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/LAW-ON-SCIENTIFIC-RESEARCH-ACTIVITY.pdf>

[44] COMMISSION STAFF WORKING DOCUMENT Montenegro 2023 Report https://neighbourhood-enlargement.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-11/SWD_2023_694%20Montenegro%20report.pdf

[45] <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/hrs4r/awarded>

Academia and academic research in Montenegro

Funding for research and academia

Based on the Law on Scientific Research Activity (MSTD, 2020), funding scientific research must ensure efficiency and transparency in spending funds. Research organisations can be financed from a number of sources: national budget; their own sources (based on providing intellectual and consulting services and selling products and services); donations, sponsorships, legacies, and bequests; businesses (companies, institutions and associations); international research funds; cooperation with domestic and foreign research institutions, and others. The Strategy of scientific research activity proposed by the Council for Scientific Research Activity and adopted by the Government of Montenegro on five-year terms, determines an indicative amount of funds for financing programmes of public interest and annual plans for funding scientific research. For carrying out research of public interest as determined by the Strategy, all research organisations and researchers may secure funding from the national budget. As defined by the Law, through providing tax incentives and other measures, the government encourages investing in scientific research.

The public funding for research and development was 0.36% of GDP in 2019, and 0.50% in 2018 [46]. In 2023, the state budget for science and innovation was EUR 4.08 million. As the 2023 budget is considered a stark rise in comparison to previous years, the EU Commission explains that it not only supports the post-COVID19 economic recovery, but also aims to alleviate the expected brain drain of researchers and young people. Funding for research and academia is also supported by international collaborations, with significant contributions from organisations such as the European Investment Bank (EIB) [47] and the World Bank [48]. These investments focus on broader economic and social challenges, but also contribute to enhancing research and the academic landscape.

[46] European Commission (2023, November 8). Montenegro 2023 Report. (Report SWD(2023) 694 final). https://neighbourhood-enlargement.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-11/SWD_2023_694%20Montenegro%20report.pdf

[47] <https://www.eib.org/en/press/all/2021-419-eib-steps-up-support-for-montenegro-s-green-covid-19-recovery-with-a-eur50-million-loan-for-the-idf>

[48] <https://microdata.worldbank.org/index.php/catalog/6205>

Researchers careers and academia as a workplace

Persona of the researcher on the career ladder in the country

There are two main segments of academic researchers involved in scientific research - those employed at universities and those employed in research institutions. Academic careers, both teaching and research, are, in general, regulated by the Law on Higher Education that was enacted in 2016 (MESI, 2023) and **Conditions and Criteria for Promotion to Academia Titles** (Council of Higher Education, 2016) and the Law on scientific research (MSTD, 2020) and activities of the Council for Scientific Research Activity.

The number of teaching staff in academic institutions in Montenegro for the academic year 2022/2023 was 1298, of which 664 men and 634 women [49].

Career track for researcher in the country

Teaching careers

For career planning, it is important to note that since it has been enacted, continuously searching for optimal solutions and harmonisation with the EU academia, the Law on higher education has gone through several modifications that turned out to be on a yearly basis (MESI, 2023; Osmanović et al., 2022) [50]. Teaching career trajectories are organised in three scientific fields: 1) Natural-Mathematical, Technological, Medical and Agricultural Sciences and Architecture; 2) the Field of Social Sciences and Humanities, and 3) The Field of Arts.

There are precise criteria for awarding each academic title that are differentiated for these three academic fields. Academic titles for teaching positions are Assistant Professor, Associate Professor and Full Professor, and there is an entry associate position. The criteria for the categories of published scientific papers were precisely defined in 2019 (Council for Higher Education, 2019), including journals ranked in Web of Science and Scopus along with a catalogue of renowned international publishers.

Besides scientific research, as evidenced in papers published in journals, criteria for promotion incorporate quantification of teaching activities (based on students' evaluations and organisational unit appraisal, mentoring engagement at master and doctoral levels, i.e. there is a precise quantification for every aspect of teaching), and administrative activities (also precisely quantified for each of the administrative duties and activities). In sum, there is a minimal number of points required for each teaching title. If it happens that an academic cannot fulfil all the criteria needed to be promoted, s/he could be re-elected to the same position, under the condition that s/he has acquired at least half of the minimal points required for the present academic level.

[49] MONSTAT Statistical Yearbook 2023 <https://www.monstat.org/uploads/files/publikacije/godisnjak%202023/21.pdf>

[50] Osmanovic, S., Mol, S.T., Petrovic, I.B., Lasser, J., Pajic, S., Portoghese, I., van der Voort, C. (2022). Thriving or struggling in academia?: Assessing the (Contextual Antecedents of) Mental Well-Being of Researchers in Higher Education in Montenegro, 1st Conference of the Researcher Mental Health Observatory: Bridging Science and Practice in Supporting Researcher Mental Health (ReMO 2022), Budapest, Hungary, 25-26 August, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7530414>

Researchers careers and academia as a workplace

Research careers

Academics engaged in research are promoted to research and scientific titles, as regulated by the Law on scientific research (MSTD, 2020). Research titles are researcher and senior researcher. Scientific titles are scientific associate, senior scientific associate and scientific advisor. Scientific titles are comparable to academic teaching titles, namely: title of research associate is comparable with title of assistant professor, title of senior research associate with the title of associate professor and title of scientific advisor with the title of full professor. Academics with research and scientific titles must fulfil the requirements defined by their research organisation. The Council for Scientific Research gives an opinion on the criteria for awarding titles defined by each research organisation. Those engaged in academic research that are not employed in research organisations, can be awarded the appropriate research or scientific title at one of the universities in the country.

All academics are elected to these positions for a specified term of five years until they reach the position of full professor or scientific advisor, which is elected indefinitely (tenured positions). So, all positions are eligible for tenured status if they are elected at the public competition every five-years (meaning there is also funding available for the specified position) and provide results in line with the criteria. But it should also be noted that for each five-year term of evaluation, there is an open public competition for the specified position. As full professors and scientific advisors have indefinite, tenure positions, they are no longer evaluated in terms of these criteria.

Research has evidenced stronger intention to leave the country among people under the age of 30 [51]. Assessed emigration potential is higher among younger people with higher levels of human capital [52] which means that brain drain could also pose an obstacle to developing academic research potential.

[51] Mirković, N., Obradović, N., Četković, Ž., Đukanović, P. (2023). Young people between marginalization, radicalization, and potential. Research report. Centre for Civic Education (CEE). <https://cgo-cce.org/en/2023/08/28/young-people-between-marginalization-radicalization-and-potential/>

[52] Lavrić, M. (2019). Closer to the EU, farther from leaving. Research report. Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung. <https://library.fes.de/pdf-files/bueros/sarajevo/15555.pdf>

Researchers careers and academia as a workplace

Workplace and employment in academia

Working hours, paid daily and weekly rest, and vacation in academia are legally regulated by the Law on Labor [53], Law on Higher Education (MESI, 2023) and Law on scientific research (MSTD, 2020).

Each institution specifies these by the statute, collective agreement, and labour contract.

In the case of the University of Montenegro, the Statute [54] and the Collective agreement [55], among other issues, specify the weekly workload for academic and professional staff (from four hours of lectures for full professors, associate professors, assistant professors, and researchers to 22 hours in the teaching process for senior lab technicians and lab technicians).

All other activities (teaching, research, and administrative) are carried out as part of the 40 hours working week for full-time employees. Academics from the University should also spend at least 30% of their working hours on scientific research.

The working schedule is determined by the decision of the Rector. The right to a sabbatical year is granted to academics holding the titles of associate professor and full professor every seven years.

Stakeholders and policies

Actively engaged in improving employment and working conditions and research careers at universities, the University of Montenegro and the Euraxess Network in Montenegro promote the European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for their Recruitment [56] The University of Montenegro hosts EURAXESS services in the country [57]. University of Montenegro, University of Donja Gorica and Mediterranean University signed the Declaration of Commitment for members of the EURAXESS network.

The University of Montenegro is dedicated to open, transparent, and merit-based recruitment (OTM-R) [58]. In line with the Strategy of the University of Montenegro, there is a plan to make research positions more attractive and to encourage mobility. This, in turn, can lead to more efficient use of investments in research. The University's commitment to OTM-R is also reflected in its HR strategy for Researchers - Action plan [59].

Montenegro is a fully associated member of Horizon Europe since January 2021 [60]. The country has taken part in the EU Research and Innovation programmes since 2008. Montenegro is also the first country from the Western Balkan region focusing on innovation as reflected in a number of SMEs participating in the Horizon 2020.

[53] Law on Labor (2021). Official Gazette of Montenegro, no. 74/2019; 008/2021; 059/2021. <https://wapi.gov.me/download/5783ef41-8afc-4cbb-88a0-dcc9ade6f670?version=1.0>

[54] Statute of the University of Montenegro (2018). Bulletin of the University of Montenegro number 337/2015;

447/2018. https://www.ucg.ac.me/skladiste/blog_6/objava_159200/fajlovi/01-1102%20Statute%20of%20the%20UNiversity%20od%20Montenegro.pdf

[55] Collective agreement of the University of Montenegro (2023). Official Gazette of Montenegro, no. 069/2016; 076/2019 and UoM Bulletin, no. 576/2023.

https://www.ucg.ac.me/skladiste/blog_6/objava_3710/fajlovi/Collective%20Agreement.pdf

[56] <https://www.euraxess.me/montenegro/news-announcements/info-day-european-charter-researchers-and-code-conduct-their>

[57] <https://www.euraxess.me/>

[58] As documented in the in the Statute of the University, criteria for academic and research promotions, selection rules, and a Code of professional ethics.

[59] <https://www.ucg.ac.me/objava/blog/17/objava/39887>

[60] https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/europe-world/international-cooperation/association-horizon-europe/montenegro_en

Mental health support and service systems in academia

At the University of Montenegro (UCG), the oldest and largest university in the country, there is a Center for International Cooperation and Career Development [61] that primarily offers services to students of UMNE, but it is also envisaged to serve the academic staff. The Center is also engaged in supporting early career researchers. Under the Centre, there is The International Relations and Mobility Office that supports academic staff in applying and taking part in international projects and programs as well as teaching staff mobility.

The Department for Language Support in Internationalisation assists scientific, teaching and non-teaching staff, as well as foreign guest lecturers, researchers, and students, in developing needed language proficiency. The newest part of the Centre, Project Office (established in 2022) is the main support point for academics in all issues related to project management, from disseminating information about calls for international cooperation and related training, to providing guidance and support in all steps of project management.

At the University of Donja Gorica, as a part of the Applied Psychology study program, students established an association that evolved into the Centre for Mental Health devoted to the promotion, preservation, and improvement of the mental health of students, academic staff, and the community in general [62]. Among their latest projects, "MentaLink" aims to provide psychological first aid and support to students from all universities on university study issues such as anxiety and procrastination.

The University of Donja Gorica also actively took part in the first Mental Health Festival in Montenegro and similar activities aimed at promoting mental health, such as World Mental Health Day, World Suicide Prevention Day, and World Children's Day. Participating in the DigNest Erasmus+ project that supports students in developing digital technologies in priority areas of agriculture and health [63], applied psychology students presented innovative technological solutions for supporting the mental health of students.

[61] <https://www.ucg.ac.me/objava/blog/6/objava/5>
<https://www.ucg.ac.me/rektorat/karijera#lat>

[62] <https://www.udg.edu.me/>

[63] <https://dignest.me/#/>

<https://fprn.udg.edu.me/obavjestenja/6389-uspjeh-studenata-primijenjene-psihologije-na-prezentacijama-u-okviru-projekta-dign%E2%82%ACst>

Mental health support and service systems in academia

Recent research on mental health of academics

Based on the presented legal framework, and under the internationally recognizable “publish or perish” academic climate, it is visible that the working environment of academic researchers in Montenegro, particularly those employed at universities, poses high demands in the fields of teaching, research, and administrative duties and activities [64].

Findings from the research study developed as part of the REMO COST Action [65], on a sample of academics from two Montenegrin universities, suggest that it would be beneficial for mental health and preventing burnout among academics to reduce the pressures that push them to work excessively.

[64] Osmanovic, S., Mol, S.T., Petrovic, I.B., Lasser, J., Pajic, S., Portoghese, I., van der Voort, C. (2022). Thriving or struggling in academia?: Assessing the (Contextual Antecedents of) Mental Well-Being of Researchers in Higher Education in Montenegro, 1st Conference of the Researcher Mental Health Observatory: Bridging Science and Practice in Supporting Researcher Mental Health (ReMO 2022), Budapest, Hungary, 25-26 August, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7530414>

[65] Osmanovic, S., Pajic, S., Petrovic, I. B., & Portoghese, I. (2023). Workaholism, work engagement, and burnout among academics in Montenegro: A psychometric network approach. *Work*, (Preprint), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.3233/WOR-230347>

Equity, diversity and inclusion

Policies on mental health in general and health at work that are presented in the Strategy for the Protection and Improvement of Mental Health in Montenegro for 2019–2023 [66], Law on Safety and Health at Work [67] and Strategy for Improvement of Safety and Health at Work for 2016–2020 [68]. It is expected from all the stakeholders, mainly the government, trade unions, and employers, to collaborate in supporting workers safety, health, mental health, and well-being. In 2020, accelerated by the Covid-19 pandemic, the need for stronger support of mental health was initiated by UNICEF and WHO, primarily in the segment of children and adolescents [69]. It also meant initiating public discussions, including better funding, and, consequently, opening up these issues at the policy level. In general, it is recognized that reforms of the strategic and legislative framework are needed in this field.

Montenegro has actively pursued initiatives to address discrimination, promote diversity and equality, and combat hate speech [70]. Equality and prohibition of any form of discrimination, direct or indirect, on any grounds, are guaranteed by the Constitution of Montenegro [71]. The issues of academic freedoms and responsibilities, including equity, diversity, inclusion, and accessibility are founded in the Law on Labor [72], Law on Higher Education [73] and the Law on Scientific Research Activity [74]. The Law on Higher Education [75] ensures that academics have the freedom of thought and ideas; they are free to publish the results of their research, to organise and associate, and are protected from any form of discrimination.

[66] Strategija zaštite i unapređenja mentalnog zdravlja u Crnoj Gori 2019–2023

<https://www.gov.me/dokumenta/60af25aa-a65e-4957-84d8-e77a3182ab9b>

[67] Law on Safety and Health at Work

<https://osha.europa.eu/en/about-eu-osha/national-focal-points/montenegro>

[68] Predlog strategije za unapređenje zaštite i zdravlja na radu u Crnoj Gori 2016–2020 s Predlogom akcionog plana

<https://www.gov.me/dokumenta/88262366-9662-4b3e-a98a-91d315f42d8e>

[69] UNICEF Montenegro (2020, October 12). WHO and UNICEF: increase investment in mental health.

<https://www.unicef.org/montenegro/en/stories/who-and-unicef-increase-investment-mental-health>

[70] Promotion of diversity and equality in Montenegro

<https://www.coe.int/en/web/inclusion-and-antidiscrimination/hf2-montenegro>

[71] The Constitution of Montenegro, Amendments I–XVI, Official Gazette of Montenegro, nos. 1/2007, 38/2013.

<https://api.skupstina.me/media/files/1708526717-constitution-of-montenegro.pdf>

<https://api.skupstina.me/media/files/1679474894-amendments-i-to-xvi-to-the-constitution-of-montenegro.pdf>

[72] Labour Law. <https://www.gov.me/dokumenta/39fd6499-9069-48d0-a5ce-ecb04f1797ec>

Direct or indirect discrimination of persons seeking employment and employed persons, on the grounds of race, skin color, nationality, social or ethnic origin, connection with a minority nation or minority national community, language, religion or conviction, political or other belief, gender, change of sex, gender identity, sexual orientation, health condition, disability, age, financial status, marital or family status, pregnancy, membership of a group or assumption of membership of a group, political party, trade union or other organizations, or any other personal feature shall be prohibited.

[73] Law on Higher Education (2023). Official Gazette of Montenegro, No. 044/2014; 052/2014; 047/2015; 040/2016; 042/2017; 071/2017; 055/2018; 003/2019; 017/2019; 047/2019; 074/2020; 104/2021; 086/2022; 125/2023.

https://www.ucg.ac.me/skladiste/blog_6/objava_159199/fajlovi/00-0102%20Law%20on%20Higher%20Education.pdf

[74] Law on Scientific Research Activity. (2020). Official Gazette of Montenegro, No. 80/2010; 40/2011; 57/2014; and 082/2020.

<https://wapi.gov.me/download-preview/1e14d5db-4a2a-4298-9bfc-3c93d771e411?version=1.0>

[75] Law on Higher Education (2023). Official Gazette of Montenegro, No. 044/2014; 052/2014; 047/2015; 040/2016; 042/2017; 071/2017; 055/2018; 003/2019; 017/2019; 047/2019; 074/2020; 104/2021; 086/2022; 125/2023.

https://www.ucg.ac.me/skladiste/blog_6/objava_159199/fajlovi/00-0102%20Law%20on%20Higher%20Education.pdf

Equity, diversity and inclusion

The Law on Academic Integrity [76] defines and regulates issues of academic integrity. Academics are guaranteed freedom of thought and protection from discrimination. Discrimination is regulated by the protection of human rights and freedoms [77], Law on the Prohibition of Discrimination [78] and gender discrimination particularly by the Law on Gender Equality [79]. Since 2012, harassment in the workplace, including sexual harassment, has been prohibited by the Law on prohibition of harassment in the workplace [80]. Employers are obliged to protect employees' dignity, integrity, and health, including protecting them from abuse and workplace bullying. Prohibition of psychological harassment and humiliating other employees is also included in the Collective Agreement at the University of Montenegro [81].

Actively supporting wider social efforts devoted to equality and anti-discrimination, the University of Montenegro developed the Gender Equality Plan for the period 2022-2026 [82]. In 2021, the University of Donja Gorica established the Office for Gender Equality aiming to harmonise the private and professional lives of academics and other employees [83], identifying the university as a safe and secure place, also preventing harassment and providing psychological support.

[76] Law on Academic Integrity (2019). The Official Register of Montenegro, No. 017/2019.

https://www.ucg.ac.me/skladiste/blog_6/objava_159199/fajlovi/00-0202%20The%20Law%20on%20Academic%20Integrity.pdf

[77] Law on Protector of Human Rights and Freedoms. <https://www.gov.me/dokumenta/a47deefc-eb7c-43fa-8ba1-63ff25a43f41>

[78] Law on Prohibition of Discrimination. Official Gazette of Montenegro, nos. 46/2010, 40/2011; 18/2014; 42/2017. <http://www.sluzbenilist.me/pregled-dokumenta-2/?id={7A94151E-8E30-48C3-A82A-826308643D8A}>

[79] Law on Gender Equality. Official Gazette of Republic of Montenegro, nos. 46/2007; 73/2010; 40/2010; 35/2015. <http://www.sluzbenilist.me/pregled-dokumenta-2/?id={E7389CBA-854C-4122-8510-720BA6C989A3}>

[80] Government of Montenegro. (2012). Law on prohibition of harassment in the workplace Official gazette of Montenegro no. 030/2012 and 054/2016.

[81] Collective Agreement at the University of Montenegro.

https://www.ucg.ac.me/skladiste/blog_6/objava_3710/fajlovi/Kolektivni%20Ugovor%20Univerziteta%20Crne%20Gore.pdf

[82] GENDER EQUALITY PLAN 2022-2026

[https://www.ucg.ac.me/skladiste/blog_1023/objava_152210/fajlovi/PLAN%20RODNE%20RAVNOPRAVNOSTI%20UCG%202022-2026\(2\).pdf](https://www.ucg.ac.me/skladiste/blog_1023/objava_152210/fajlovi/PLAN%20RODNE%20RAVNOPRAVNOSTI%20UCG%202022-2026(2).pdf)

[83] <https://www.google.com/url?q=https://www.udg.edu.me/obavjestenja/osnovana-kancelarija-za-rodnu-ravnopravnost-na-univerzitetu-donja-gorica-1852&sa=D&source=docs&ust=1713002994201884&usq=AOvVaw3HnPleQGDHNE862T-L5555>

National culture

It could prove beneficial to review the policies, legal frameworks, and practices related to academic work, researchers' careers, and their mental health from the perspective of the national culture.

For those interested in the prevailing culture of Montenegro, based on Hofstede's findings on cultural dimensions [84], it is interesting to note that Montenegro scores high on power distance and collectivism and low on indulgence.

Source: <https://www.hofstede-insights.com/country-comparison-tool?countries=montenegro>

In a nutshell

The issue of mental health in general, and particularly in academia, is not being adequately addressed. The complex and sensitive issues surrounding mental health protection should be considered while developing all national strategies.

As evidenced by numerous amendments to laws, the country is undergoing a period of all encompassing changes that have been additionally intensified by the process of accession to the EU. Clearly, these changes put pressure on academics and pose additional sources of stress. Thus, thinking of researchers' well-being, it would be beneficial to conclude processes that contribute to job and career uncertainty and insecurity.

The challenges of the contemporary world demand changes, but in order to support the careers of academics, their mental health and wellbeing, these challenges should not be sources of stress and strain and continuously growing job demands. In order to support adherence to society-wide sustainable development and innovation, it is essential to support the mental health and wellbeing of academics.

